

Green Management of Human Resources in Industrial Organizations: Case of the Tunisian Chemical Group (TCG)

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Abstract:

Background: The industrial sector is recognized for its harmful effect on the environment, which requires intense reflection on the establishment of a sustainable and environmentally friendly business model. Indeed, industrial organizations are forced to develop green human resource management (GHRM) as a fundamental application of HRM to degrade the harmful impact caused by industrial activities.

Objective: The central objective of this research is to examine the relationship between green skills, green motivation and the involvement of green employees, with environmental performance, and see how the company can improve its environmental performance.

Methods: The method used is quantitative and the data are collected through a questionnaire. Structural equation modeling (PLS) was used to study a sample of 100 employees of SIAPE in Tunisia by referring to the model of (Anwar and Al, 2019).

Results: The results of the study demonstrated that green motivation and employee involvement have a positive impact on environmental performance.

Conclusions: The adoption of GHRM practices can be successfully implemented if the company encourages employee motivation and gives them the opportunity to participate in the organization's green initiative. In addition, the Tunisian state must further strengthen the green environment through new regulations while keeping in mind the following attribute: We must think about future generations.

Keywords: OCBE ; Environment performance ; Green employee ; Green motivation ; GRHM

I. Introduction

The industry is facing the challenge of regulatory enforcement related to environmental issues such as waste management, global warming, and limited natural resources. Environmental awareness is increasing worldwide to push the industry to adopt a green industry by complying with the concept of Green Manufacturing (Ghazilla et al., 2015). However, industrial organizations that implement Green Manufacturing are still very rare. Most industrialists consider the application of Green Manufacturing as a factor that hinders the realization of profits rather than a means of development (Rehman et al., 2013). Indeed, green manufacturing is becoming one of the obstacles, including in Tunisia. Other barriers to the application of Green Manufacturing include limited awareness about the "green" trend, limited access to literature on Green Manufacturing, lack of knowledge about this field, as well as scarcity of information regarding the implementation of Green Manufacturing in companies (Sangwan and Mittal, 2015).

Industrial organizations are aware of the regulations and their environmental responsibility and must make efforts to manage and monitor the environment. The environmental management practices that industrial organizations have been performing exogenously for years have been grouped under the specifications of the ISO 14001 Environmental Management System (EMS)

User Guide. ISO 14001 defines the basic elements of an effective environmental management system, including the resources needed to improve, implement, and review planning activities, organizational structure, responsibilities, procedures, processes, and environmental policy (Polat Dede, 2019). The impacts of industrial companies on the environment are documented through all Green Manufacturing practices and contribute to the economy.

Green human resource management (GHRM) suggests an effort to improve HRM applications to alleviate the damage that can be caused by the activities of companies in all their business processes (Zaid, Bon & Jaaron, 2018). Employees' eco-responsible behavior develops the environmental performance of the company (Lo et al., 2012). GHRM influences employees' eco-responsible behavior to achieve ecological sustainability (Y. J. Kim et al., 2019). Thus, GHRM policies should be put into practice to improve environmental performance by promoting employee engagement practices and their eco-responsible behavior, that is, striving to respect nature and the environment to the maximum. Moreover, previous studies have demonstrated that employees' eco-responsible behavior is one of the outcomes related to engagement at the organizational level.

The fundamental contribution of this research is to provide an understanding of how to implement GHRM practices in an industrial organization while improving environmental performance through employee behavior, also called organizational citizenship behavior toward the environment (OCBE). Anwar et al (2019) suggested that OCBE is an action taken voluntarily by employees to achieve the environmental performance of companies. This study will focus on green HRM practices and employees that are exerted in the industrial sector to improve sustainability. The objectives of this research include seven components: (1) to study the relationship between green skills development practices and organizational citizenship behavior toward the environment; (2) to examine green motivation enhancement practices and OCBE; (3) to study green employee involvement practices and OCBE; (4) to find out the relationship between OCBE and environmental performance; (5) to see the mediation effect of OCBE between green skills development practices and environmental performance; (6) to study the mediation of OCBE with green motivation improvement practices and environmental performance; (7) to examine the mediation of OCBE with green employee involvement practices and environmental performance.

II. Literature Review

Green HRM is understood by the concept of the theory of abilities, motivation and opportunities (AMO). AMO is one of the most popular theories to describe and understand the concept of HRM in the company (Appelbaum, 2000). However, AMO has become one of the most used bases for modeling employee performance (Tuuli, M. M., 2012). (Armstrong & Brown, 2019) revealed that performance depends on the employee's ability, motivation and opportunity as follows: ability to do the job (skills, abilities), motivation to do the job and opportunity to perform. Employee performance can be measured with these three components: having the necessary skills, giving appropriate motivation and providing an opportunity to participate (Marin Garcia, 2016). (Ahmed and Hassan, 2023) demonstrated that green HRM practices have a positive significance on improving organizational performance, especially regarding environmental sustainability and employee productivity. However, and according to the study of (Martinez and Ramachandran, 2023) explored the effects of green HRM in emerging economies such as the Tunisian case and they highlighted that green HRM can significantly improve organizational performance by reducing environmental impact and strengthening employee engagement. In addition, a recent study conducted by (Lee and Kim, 2024) who gave a current state of research in the field of green HRM and its effects on organizational performance. Indeed, they confirmed that green HRM practices contribute to

better environmental and operational performance, positively affecting employee morale and organizational reputation.

AMO theory announces that HRM that improves employees' abilities, motivation, and opportunities leads to OCBE. Employee OCBE is one of the commonalities between high-performing employees and organizational performance (Anwar et al., 2019). The conceptual models of this research are presented in Figure 1

What is remarkable is that there is a need for further studies to complete the model of our research in order to arrive at the model that is most suited to the AMO theory to better understand green HRM. The mediation of OCBE between the green HRM relationship and environmental performance is often underestimated. (Harvey et Al, 2013) revealed that green HRM can produce long-term results if we find solutions for the mediation of OCBE.

The relationship between green skills (capacity) building practices and OCBE

(Siyambalapitiya et al, 2018) suggested that environmental policy, green image and environmental performance can be advertised to attract suitable candidates. (Zibarras and Coan, 2015) revealed that green hiring is one of the important phases of HRM practices, important for organizations to recruit employees interested in environmental issues to improve the environmental performance of the company. Involving all employees in green initiatives will enhance the possibilities of evolving their capabilities. Therefore, training and development are necessary to increase the skills, awareness and knowledge of employees to carry out environmental activities (Mousa et al., 2019). Green training is about promoting knowledge about the environment. Indeed, it can help staff to link knowledge to behavior. However, and to improve the environmental performance of the organization, it is necessary to provide employees with environmental knowledge. In this research, we investigate whether green skills have a significant impact on employees' green skills practices and OCBE.

H1: Green skills-building practices are significantly related to OCBE

The relationship between green motivation enhancement practices and OCBE

(Harvey et Al, 2013) revealed that green motivation enhances all actions to motivate employees to align their behavior with the company's environmental goals. Moreover, (Yong and Mohd-Yosoff, 2016) demonstrated that when the company provides rewards to employees for any environmental behavior will increase commitment to environmental responsibility and contribute to the organization's citizenship behavior environment (Govindarajulu & Daily, 2004). Combined financial and non-financial rewards are more effective in motivating employees to get involved in the company's environmental activities (Renwick et al., 2013). Developing a reward and skill system will motivate employees to engage in the company's environmental initiatives (Mousa and Othman, 2019). In this research, we analyze the relationship between green employee motivation practices and OCBE

H2: Green motivation-enhancing practices are significantly related to OCBE

Relationship between green employee involvement practices (opportunity) and OCBE

(Tang and al, 2017) revealed that among the important dimensions of GHRM is green involvement. Employees have the opportunity to participate in environmental management to encourage them to maintain pollution prevention and exploit environmental opportunities. In addition, creating a climate of mutual learning will effectively strengthen employees' green behavior and awareness. The atmosphere in which employees operate can enhance their awareness of environmental issues. Working with others can provide employees with the

opportunity to share their knowledge, experience, and solutions (Daily and al., 2007). In this research, we verify the relationship between green employee involvement practices and OCBE.

H3: Green employee involvement practices are significantly related to OCBE

The relationship between OCBE and environmental performance

(Paille and al, 2014) explained that OCBE reflects an employee's behavior in performing actions beyond expectations that benefit the natural environment. Indeed, the essential factor to support environmental performance is the employee's willingness to engage in pro-environmental behaviors such as OCBE. (Paille and al, 2014) also stated that OCBE is positively related to environmental performance. In this research, we examine the relationship between OCBE and environmental performance.

H4: OCBE is significantly related to environmental performance

The mediating role of OCBE

The role of HR practices is to implement an environment that encourages authoritarian citizenship behavior among representatives with the final goal that when workers review their work needs to invest additional energy, help their colleagues and support hierarchical activities, at that time, the level of hierarchical execution degree should be high (Messersmith and al, 2011). OCBE is considered as a mediator between the HR-ecology action components (Paillé and al., 2014). (Paillé and al, 2014) examined the relationship between strategic HRM, OCBE and the environmental performance of the company. The results of the examination revealed that HRM is related to the environmental performance of an organization, while OCBE is conceived as a mediator between HRM and environmental performance. (Alt and Spitzack, 2016) demonstrated that employees with better green competence have higher environmental performance through the indication of OCBE. Moreover, (Pinzone and al, 2016) stated that green HRM is related to OCBE, while for (Daily and al, 2009) revealed that OCBE incentivizes environmental performance, so OCBE is presented as a tool for interpreting green HRM practices to improve environmental performance.

Following this analysis, we further present the following hypotheses:

H5: OCBE significantly mediates the relationship between green skills building practices and environmental performance

H6: OCBE significantly mediates the relationship between green motivation building practices and environmental performance

H7: OCBE significantly mediates the relationship between green employee involvement practices and environmental performance

III. Research methods

The quantitative study is the most appropriate to explain the effect between the variables through hypothesis testing. Questionnaires were distributed to 100 employees who work at the SIAPE, one of the industrial companies in Tunisia that produces various types of granular, coated and uncoated fertilizers. These products cause air, water and land pollution.

The exogenous variables are green skills (X1), green motivation (X2) and green employee involvement (X3). The mediating variable is OCBE (X4) and environmental performance (Y) is identified as an endogenous variable.

The five-point Likert scale was used to measure the research items, 1 represents strongly disagree and 5 represents strongly agree. The measurement items were adapted from (Anwar and al, 2019). The sample data were obtained with a systematic random sampling technique.

Validity and reliability tests were conducted and the variables that have validity scores up to 0.6 were retained. Since our sample is fixed at 100 respondents, a structural equation model (SEM) with partial least squares (PLS) was applied to analyze the model. However, (Al-Dhaafri and al, 2016) suggested that PLS-SEM is commonly used for complex models that have causal relationships to be able to measure latent variables. In addition, the validity and reliability tests of the model were confirmed by evaluating the measurement model before hypothesis testing. The conceptual model of this study is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Green Humain Management Model (Anwar and Al, 2019)

RESULTS

The respondents to this study are 100 employees of a company belonging to the Tunisian chemical group producing phosphoric acid, fertilizers, ammonium phosphates, ammonium nitrates, calcium phosphates and triple super phosphate. This company belongs to the Tunisian state.

Some characteristics were used according to age, education and working period. The characteristics of the sample are described as follows: 16% of respondents are under 30 years old, 38% of respondents are between 30 and 44 years old, 42% of respondents are between 45 and 55 years old and 4% of respondents are over 55 years old. For the characteristics according to education, 78% of respondents have a baccalaureate and 22% have a level below the baccalaureate.

Reliability of the indicator

The value that is close to 1 means that there is a strong relationship between the attributes of the variable. The results of the first iteration in Table 1, shows that the values of 2.2/ 2.3/ 4.1/ 4.2 and 5.3 are less than 0.7, which results that the attributes have an insignificant contribution to the variable. The other values are at 0.7, which represents that the attributes have a significant contribution to the measured variables.

Table N°1: Outer Loading (Final)

Green Competencies	Green Motivation	Green Employee	OCBE	Enviromental
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	(X1)	(X2)	Involvement (X3)	(X4)	Performance (Y1)
1.2	0,706				
1.3	0,716				
1.4	0,887				
1.5	0,819				
1.6	0,878				
2.1		0,816			
2.4		0,789			
2.5		0,921			
2.6		0,923			
3.1			0,868		
3.2			0,909		
3.3			0,772		
3.4			0,768		
3.5			0,771		
4.3				0,82	
				2	
4.4				0,82	
				6	
4.5				0,77	
				9	
4.6				0,83	
				4	
4.7				0,88	
				8	
4.8				0,87	
				8	
4.9				0,88	
				3	
4.10				0,92	
				0	
5.1					0,844
5.4					0,794
5.5					0,844
5.6					0,768
5.7					0,845
5.8					0,859
5.9					0,855
5.10					0,840
5.11					0,754
5.12					0,887
5.13					0,902
5.14					0,886

After 4 iterations, the model no longer has any attributes that have values lower than 0.7, which will allow us to present the final model of our research in Figure 2

Figure 2: Final Model

After removing the insignificant attribute from the questionnaire, the Cronbach's alpha value for the variables Green Competence, Green Motivation, Green Employee Involvement, OCBE, and Environmental Performance are greater than 0.6, so it can be concluded that the items adopted in the questionnaire are reliable for our research. The composite reliability value for all variables is greater than 0.7 (see Table 2), and the AVE value for all variables exceeds the acceptance value of 0.5, which means that the information collected through our questionnaire is reliable.

Table N°2 : Construct Reliability and Validity

	Alpha Gronbach	Composite reliability	AVE
Green competencies (X1)	0.933	0.903	0.713
Green motivation (X2)	0.899	0.924	0.728
Green employee involvement (X3)	0.847	0.881	0.614
OCBE (X4)	0.917	0.925	0.719
Environmental performance (Y)	0.941	0.949	0.708

Discriminant Validity

According to (Ferdinand, 2006), the validity test is commonly used to measure research tools (in our case it is a questionnaire). Indeed, there are many types of validity tests, thus, discriminant validity is carried out to measure the validity of research tools.

In Table 3 we will provide the results of discriminant validity tests that are accepted. Knowing that this test is carried out following the Fornell-Larker criteria.

TableN°3 : Discriminant Validity Table

	Green competency (X1)	Green motivation (X2)	Green employee Involvement (X3)	OCBE (X4)	Environment performance (Y)
Green competency (X1)	0.818				
Green motivation (X2)	0.545	0.861			
Green employee Involvement (X3)	0.746	0.717	0.810		
OCBE (X4)	0.628	0.587	0.742	0.849	
Environment Performance (Y)	0.723	0.818	0.901	0.712	0.835

After fulfilling all the discriminant validity criteria, it can be stated that the diagonal, which is the value of the square root of the AVE, is greater than the correlation score, and therefore the model is validated and accepted.

R squared (R 2)

The R2 value of our model is 0.897, this value means the prediction of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable (environmental performance). Table 4 highlights the high criterion of the R2 value of our model.

Table N°4 : R2 TABLE

R2	Creterion
>0.75	High
>0.5	Moderate
>0.25	Low

(Sleimiet and Emeagwali, 2017)

Path coefficient

In table 5 there is the result of path coefficient that determines the test of the hypotheses presented before and analyzes the relationship between the variables

Table N°5 : Path Coefficient

	Original Sample	St-Dev	T-Value	P-Value
Green competency – Environmental performance	0.085	0.059	1.321	0.124
Green competency - OCBE	0.223	0.139	1.548	0.101
Green employee Involvement –	0.421	0.071	6.578	0.000

Environmental performance				
Green employee Involvement - OCBE	0.488	0.178	2.721	0.005
Green motivation – environmental performance	0.327	0.059	5.538	0.000
Green motivation - OCBE	0.050	0.118	0.401	0.674
OCBE – Environmental performance	0.061	0.057	1.113	0.28

In the above table, we notice the P Value < 5% and the T Value > 1.96 and we conclude that green employee involvement and green motivation have a significant impact on environmental performance and also we notice that only green employee involvement has a significant impact on OCBE as a moderator variable.

Effect size

The effect size identifies the contribution of exogenous variables to endogenous variables. However, the higher the value of the effect size, the more interesting the contribution of exogenous variables to endogenous variables.

In Table 6 the effect size criterion is presented.

Table N°6 : Effect size table

	Green competency (X1)	Green motivation (X2)	Green employee Involvement (X3)	OCBE (X4)	Environmental performance (Y)
Green competency (X1)				0.251	0.111
Green motivation (X2)				0.050	0.391
Green employee Involvement (X3)				0.511	0.551
OCBE (X4)					0.061
Environmental performance (Y)					

Table N°7 : Effect size criterion (Sleimiet and Emeagwali, 2017)

R2	Criterion
>0.75	High
>0.5	Moderate
>0.25	Low

In the table above, we find that green employee involvement has a moderate effect on predicting environmental performance and the moderating variable OCBE. However, the other variables have a weak impact on predicting environmental performance and OCBE

Indirect Effect

The indirect effect allows us to know whether the moderating factor (OCBE) mediates the relationship between green skills, green motivation and green employee involvement, and environmental performance. Table 8 shows the result of the indirect effect analysis

Table N°8 : Indirect Effects

	T-Value	P-Value
Green competency – OCBE – Environmental performance	0.876	0.363
Green employee involvement – OCBE – Environmental performance	0.763	0.429
Green motivation – OCBE – Environmental performance	0.287	0.735

The results in Table 8 demonstrated that all the P Value values are greater than 5% which results that the OBCE variable did not significantly moderate the relationship between the exogenous variable and the endogenous variable.

IV. Discussion

Returning to the PLS results in Figure 3, it can be explored that employee involvement has a very important role in determining the ecological performance of the employees of the organization. Indeed, it has the most important value (0.551) compared to ecological competence and ecological motivation in terms of exogenous variables. In addition, the value of 0.561 in employee involvement develops a moderate correlation and impact on environmental performance, while the values of 0.391 for (ecological motivation) and 0.111 (green competence) affirm that these two variables do not have a significant effect.

From the above result, OCBE has no significant impact on moderating the relationship between green competence, green motivation and employee involvement, with environmental performance. We can see that the p-value of all indirect effects of each variable has a value greater than 5%, which means that OCBE has no significant effect on moderating these variables. Table 9 shows the result of hypothesis testing, green employee involvement practices have a significant effect on environmental performance (H3). Thus, Hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted.

Table N°9 : Results (Direct effets)

Variables of model	Hypothesis	Explication
Green competency	H1 : Not valid Green competency don't have a significant effect on environmental performance	Lack of impact of knowledge on environmental performance. Insufficient awareness of the issues
Green motivation	H2 : Not valid	Green motivation don't have a significant impact
Green employee Involvement	H3 : Valid	Green employee involvement has a very important role in determining the green performance of the organization's employees. It has the highest value (0.561).
OCBE	H4 : Not valid	Not significant impact on environmental performance

Table N°10 : Results (Indirect effets)

Hypothesis	Explication
H5 : Not valid	OCBE has no significant impact on mediating the relationship between ecological competence, ecological motivation and employee involvement, with environmental performance. The p-value of all indirect effects of each variable has a value greater than 5%, which means that OCBE had no significant effect on mediating these variables.
H6 : Not valid	
H7 : Not valid	

Interpretation for Tables:

Lack of impact of knowledge on environmental performance: Employees do not translate their knowledge into effective actions to improve environmental performance.

Lack of awareness of the issues: Although they know what to do, they lack awareness of the importance and the underlying reasons for these actions.

(Anwar et Al, 2019), and following his research, was able to show that green employee involvement, green motivation and green competence have a significant effect on environmental performance. The same research revealed that OCBE has an important role in moderating green employee involvement, green motivation, green competence and environmental performance.

This article shows results for an industrial company since the industrial sector is the largest contributor to environmental degradation. The research results demonstrated that employee involvement and green motivation have a positive impact on predicting employee performance, but employee involvement has a moderate impact. In addition, green motivation has a weak

effect on environmental performance. However, OCBE has no significant impact on moderating the exogenous variables (green competence, green motivation, employee involvement) with the endogenous variable (environmental performance). The final result of the research model was presented in Figure 2.

Further analysis, the variable of green employee involvement with items 3.1/ 3.2/ 3.3/ 3.4 and 3.5 are the significant elements that affect employee performance, the respective values of the factors are 0.868; 0.828; 0.910; 0.763 and 0.776.

3.1 represent the development vision to guide environmental management actions in an organization.

3.2 represent the involvement of employees in the environmental activities of a company.

3.3 explain the formal or informal communication channels to spread green culture in organizations.

3.4 represent the degree to which the company has encouraged employees to get involved in quality improvement and problem solving on environmental issues, and the last point

3.5 represent the opportunities provided to employees to participate in environmental management such as suggestion programs, community environmental awareness programs, and green initiatives. The five points identify the strong correlation with the prediction of green employee involvement. Understanding the elements of green employee involvement and the correlation with environmental performance will allow the organization to understand how to grow in business while minimizing the negative impact on the environment.

On the green motivation side, 2.5/ 2.6/ 2.1 and 2.4 have a significant impact in terms of green motivation with respective values of 0.942; 0.939; 0.828 and 0.807.

2.5 And **2.6** determine the financial incentives and rewards to promote environmental behavior. Item **2.1** indicate whether there is a green performance indicator in the performance management and evaluation system.

Item **2.4** indicate the benefits of green travel in the company. As we can see from the research results, financial incentives and rewards are the most important aspects to increase green motivation. The financial aspect is one of the most influential factors in determining employees' motivation to adopt environmental practices. Rewards and appreciation of employees who take green measures can motivate employees to do them regularly and become habits.

For environmental performance, items 5.13/ 5.14/ 5.12/ 5.8/ 5.10/ 5.9/ 5.7/ 5.1/ 5.5/ 5.4/ and 5.11 have respective values 0.911; 0.910; 0.892; 0.873; 0.865; 0.861; 0.840; 0.834; 0.830; 0.767 and 0.746

Items **5.13/ 5.12** and **5.14** indicates the organization's activities to promote environmental awareness. Then, items **5.8/ 5.10** and **5.9** represent the practices related to the company's efforts to reduce air, water and land pollution.

The company's granulated phosphogypsum products are represented in point 5.7. The company's policies and sanctions regarding environmental behavior can be explained in points 5.1 and 5.11. Points 5.4 and 5.5 represent the energy consumption and water consumption in the organization.

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCBE) towards the environment does not have a moderating effect between green competence, green motivation and employee involvement and environmental performance. It can be concluded that organizational behavior towards the environment does not have a significant effect on the environmental performance of the organization. Companies can carry out environmental activities provided that their employees are involved in these activities and are motivated to do them otherwise it is difficult for organizations to improve their environmental performance. Based on the respondents, it can be concluded that before carrying out environmental activities, organizations must ensure that their employees have the motivation and opportunity to carry out environmental activities.

The study reveals that employee involvement is about their opportunity to participate in environmental activities, the clarity of the company's environmental vision and the issue of communication. It is important for an organization to communicate its vision and give the employee the opportunity to get involved in the organization's environmental activities and encourage employees to participate in discussions related to the green environment.

Moreover, the research has explored that employees having the motivation and opportunity to get involved in environmental activities have a strong relationship with their environmental performance. However Green competence has no significant impact on environmental performance, that is, the knowledge possessed by employees has not really improved their environmental performance, and even they know how to do it but do not have enough awareness of why these things are essential to do, it has not had a significant impact on their environment.

V. Conclusion

The adoption of green HRM practices can be successfully implemented if the company encourages employee motivation and gives them the opportunity to participate in the organization's green initiative. Among the most important aspects to motivate employees to achieve environmental performance is the financial aspect. Providing the opportunity and involvement to employees participating in the organization's green initiatives will promote the success of the implementation of environmental performance. This will help companies promote green culture at all levels of the organization. In Tunisia there are not enough regulations aimed at controlling the environment, the Tunisian state must further strengthen the green environment through new regulations so that organizations begin to implement policies and initiatives aimed at supporting environmental performance and the ecological aspect of the company while keeping in mind the following attribute: **We must think of future generations.**

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